

Oxidation of 3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-diarylpiperidin-4-ones by Thallium(III) Acetate : A Structure—Reactivity Correlation

(MRS.) KR. MEENAL* and (MRS.) S. LALITHA

Department of Chemistry, Seethalakshmi Ramaswami College (Autonomous), Tiruchirapalli-620 002

Manuscript received 11 November 1992, accepted 7 January 1993

The present work has been undertaken to study the structure-activity relationship in the thallium(III) acetate oxidation of 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diarylpiperidin-4-ones and for this purpose six aryl-substituted-piperidones have been prepared following the procedure available in literature¹. Kabbe² postulated, later confirmed by Henry³ that $Tl(OAc)_2^+$ is the most reactive species. The low reactivity observed substantiates the non-chair conformation⁴. Further, the effect of electron-attracting and electron-donating groups at *ortho*- and *para*-positions in the phenyl ring for comparison has been explored.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of oxidation of 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diarylpiperidin-4-ones (1–7) by thallium(III) acetate in aqueous acetic acid in the presence of sulphuric acid have been investigated under pseudo-first order conditions with the substrate in large excess and the results are presented in Table 1. The data indicate that (i) the oxidation reaction is first order dependent on both oxidant and substrate, (ii) the reaction

is acid-catalysed and the order with respect to H^+ varies from 0.4 to 0.9, (iii) the rate decreases with increase in solvent polarity showing that the charge density in the transition state is less than that in the reactants and (iv) addition of sodium sulphate seems to have negligible effect on the reaction rate conforming ion-dipole reaction. Activation parameters (Table 2) were obtained by running the reaction at four different temperatures. Table 2 also records second order rate constants, obtained by the division of the pseudo-first order rate constants by the concentration of the substrate.

Mechanism and rate law : The non-appearance of polymer on the addition of acrylonitrile monomer to the reaction mixture rules out free radical mechanism. The stoichiometry (1 : 1) and the product acyloin isolated and characterised by the usual spectral data coupled with the kinetic results given, led us to propose the mechanism in the scheme for the oxidation (Scheme 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [SUBSTRATE], [Tl^{III}], [H⁺] AND HOAc ON THE RATE AT 328 K

[Substrate] (10 ² mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁵ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)				
	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃
1.5	2.98	1.94	1.33	3.13	2.24
2.0	3.76	2.55	1.80	4.20	2.85
2.5	4.75	3.30	2.18	5.08	3.68
3.0	5.60	3.98	2.63	6.28	4.25
[Substrate]=2 × 10 ⁻² mol dm ⁻³ , [H ⁺]=1.5 mol dm ⁻³ , 80% (v/v) HOAc-H ₂ O					
[Tl ^{III}] (10 ³ mol dm ⁻³)	1.5	2.50	1.79	3.92	2.76
2.0	3.76	2.55	1.80	4.20	2.85
2.5	3.90	2.47	1.79	4.05	2.70
3.0	3.54	2.46	1.84	4.17	2.82
[Substrate]=2 × 10 ⁻² mol dm ⁻³ , [Tl ^{III}]=2 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³ , 80% (v/v) HOAc-H ₂ O					
[H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	1.0	2.23	1.59	3.54	2.08
1.5	3.76	2.55	1.80	4.20	2.85
2.0	3.97	3.10	2.99	5.21	3.91
2.5	4.49	3.47	3.26	5.71	4.51
[Substrate]=2 × 10 ⁻² mol dm ⁻³ , [Tl ^{III}]=2 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³ , [H ⁺]=1.5 mol dm ⁻³					
% HOAc	75	2.00	1.73	3.03	2.53
80	3.76	2.55	1.80	4.20	2.85
85	3.88	2.93	2.72	6.63	3.79
90	4.86	3.94	3.39	8.94	5.38

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF COMPOUNDS 1-7 AT 328 K

Compd. no.	10 ³ k ₂ mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹	E _a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔS [‡] JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
1	2.08	82.5	79.8	97.4	53.6 ^a
2	5.03	29.8	27.1	95.0	207.0
3	1.88	68.7	66.0	97.7	96.6
4	1.28	69.4	66.7	98.7	97.6
5	0.90	60.4	57.7	99.7	128.0
6	2.11	52.0	49.3	97.4	146.6
7	1.43	71.7	69.0	98.4	89.6

*Ref. 6.

R = CH₃

- 1; X₁=X₂=H
 2; X₁=NO₂, X₂=H
 3; X₁=Cl, X₂=H
 4; X₁=CH₃, X₂=H
 5; X₁=OCH₃, X₂=H
 6; X₁=H, X₂=CH₃
 7; X₁=H, X₂=OCH₃

The rate law for this mechanism is given in equation (1),

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]}{dt} = k[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}][\text{substrate}][\text{H}^+] \quad (1)$$

The concentration of H⁺ remaining constant during the entire run, the rate law reduces to equation (2),

$$\text{Rate} = k[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}][\text{substrate}] \quad (2)$$

Under the experimental conditions Tl(OAc)₂⁺ seems to be most active electrophilic species in the oxidation which is made more polar^{3,5} by the sulphuric acid present in the medium. It is further substantiated by the rate dependence on the dielectric constant of the medium.

Scheme 1

Structure and reactivity: All the compounds investigated have been shown to exist in the non-chair or twist conformation. 3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-diphenyl piperidin-4-ones ($k_2(3,8\text{K})=7.67 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) reacts with Tl^{III} twenty times slower than 3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones ($k_2(318\text{K})=1.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and such a retardation in the rate indicates that there should be greater steric crowding in the transition state than in the ground state which is possible only when the third step is rate-limiting. The rate retardation, however, can better be rationalised on the basis of the decreased non-bonded-gauche interactions between OH and CH₃ groups in the enolic form, which is possible only in highly distorted chair or twist conformation. The electrophilic attack of Tl^{III} seems to be regio-selective. The positively charged active species is led to the reaction site through the π-electron cloud of the aryl

ring probably by concerted tour mechanism. The oxidation process can take place by a pathway in which a positive species migrates in a stepwise fashion from one nucleophilic position to another. The *ortho*-substituted aryl ring being in the tilted position will not be in the same plane with the double bond in the twist form. The substituent in the *ortho*-position sterically hinders the coplanarity of the aryl ring with the double bond. Subsequently, approach of the oxidant to the double bond is partially retarded as found in the case of *o*-Cl, *o*-CH₃ and *o*-OCH₃. In the case of *o*-NO₂, the nitro group being highly electron-attracting, outweighs the hindrance and thereby enhances the rate of oxidation but it is not the case with *o*-Cl substituent. Electron-donating methyl and methoxyl groups increase the π -electron cloud in the aryl ring and retains the oxidising species and slowly releases it to attack and hence decreases the rate. The unexpected slow rate in methoxyl compared to that of methyl derives support from the concerted tour mechanism. The lone-pair of electrons on oxygen atom in the methoxyl group competes with the reaction site. The concerted tour mechanism coupled with the orientation of aryl ring coplanar with the double bond influence the rate of oxidation as observed in the case of *para*-substituents. The reactivity observed follows the order: p -CH₃ \approx H > p -OCH₃. The unexpected retardation by p -OCH₃ may be attributed to the presence of oxygen lone-pair electrons as found in the case of *o*-OCH₃. The inductive effect of p -CH₃ substituent facilitates the formation of oxythallation adduct and this enhances the rate of oxidation. The effect of electron-attracting substituents such as p -NO₂, p -Cl etc. on the rate of oxidation could not be studied due

to very poor solubility of these substituted piperidones.

Experimental

Kinetic run: Thallic acetate was prepared from thallic oxide and was standardised iodometrically. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Kinetic experiments were carried out titrimetrically. The course of reaction was followed by estimating the unconsumed Tl^{III} iodometrically. The concentration of the piperidone was always maintained high so that the pseudo-first order rate could be applied. The pseudo-first order rate constants were evaluated by the method of least-squares.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Managing Trustee for facilities and the faculty members for constant encouragement. The authors are indebted to their colleague Dr. N. Radha for her stimulating discussions and Dr. T. R. Padmini for her kind help.

References

1. M. BALASUBRAMANIAN and N. PADMA, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 2135.
2. H. J. KABBE, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1962, 656, 204.
3. P. M. HENRY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 1597.
4. M. JAMBULINGAM, P. NANJAPPAN, K. NATARAJAN and K. RAMALINGAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, 25, 390; N. SIVAKUMAR, J. NAGALINGAM, A. M. PALANISAMY, V. PREMKUMAR, K. NATARAJAN, M. JAMBULINGAM and P. NANJAPPAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1985, 24, 531.
5. P. S. R. KRISHNAMURTHY and S. N. PATI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, 16, 139.
6. KR. MEENAL and S. LALITHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, 69, 741.